

ENHANCING A BALANCED EDUCATION FOR HOLISTIC DEVELOPMENT: BOOKER T. WASHINGTON'S *UP FROM SLAVERY*

Komi BEGEDOU

komi.begedou@gmail.com

University of Lomé, Togo

ABSTRACT

Education can be considered as the process of receiving or giving systematic instructions. However, it goes beyond the mere study and mastery of knowledge and skills, aiming at changing lives and pushing students to take actions susceptible of contributing to both personal growth and community development. This paper mainly discusses the contribution of education in the promotion of holistic development, with a focus on Booker T. Washington's *Up From Slavery*. Hinging on educational philosophy in Washington's autobiography, the paper analyzes the interplay of cognitive development, vocational training, and moral values in shaping the progress of formerly colonized peoples. Through the critical lens of postcolonial theory, the study scrutinizes the strategies used by the writer to ensure sound education for individual fulfillment and societal growth. It aims to promote a holistic approach to education in the building of modern African societies.

Keywords: education, elite, hand, heart, development

RESUME

L'éducation peut être considérée comme le processus consistant à recevoir ou à donner des instructions systématiques. Cependant, elle va au-delà de la simple étude et de la maîtrise des connaissances et des compétences, visant à changer les vies et à amener les apprenants à prendre des mesures susceptibles de contribuer à la fois à l'épanouissement personnel et au développement de la communauté. Cet article traite principalement de la contribution de l'éducation à la promotion d'un développement holistique, telle que présentée dans *Up From Slavery* de Booker T. Washington. S'appuyant sur la philosophie de l'éducation dans l'autobiographie de Washington, l'article analyse l'interaction du développement cognitif, de la formation professionnelle et des valeurs morales sur le développement des populations anciennement colonisées. À travers le prisme de la théorie postcoloniale, l'étude passe à l'examen des stratégies utilisées par l'écrivain pour assurer une éducation solide permettant l'épanouissement individuel et sociétal. Elle vise à promouvoir une approche holistique de l'éducation dans la construction de sociétés africaines modernes.

Mots-clés : éducation, élite, main, cœur, développement

INTRODUCTION

Education is a powerful tool for continuous self-development in all societies. Its implementation in everyday life constitutes a veritable fact in the furtherance of humanity. For John Dewey, an American educational reformer, education "is a process of living and not a preparation for future living" (217). Understandably, education impacts human beings in their daily lives and in their quest for self-fulfillment. Challenging the theoretical aspect of teaching, Francis W. Porter argues: "teachers had been teaching subjects when they should have been teaching children" (Flinders and

Thomas 35). From the foregoing, Porter is of the same view with Dewey that the pursuit of a mere intellectual growth is insufficient for a well-trained individual. In other words, individuals need more than an intellectual education to be really fulfilled.

Furthermore, education is a great asset for a society when all the population get educated. In the United State, unfortunately, for a long period of time, education was exclusively the privilege of white people. This results in unbalanced relationships between the black people and the white people. As quoted by Lawrence Banais, Horace Mann posits: "if one class possesses all the wealth and education, while the residue of the society is ignorant and poor, it matters not by what name the relation between them may be called: the latter, in fact and true, will be the servile dependents and the subjects of the former" (Mann 124). Given that knowledge is power, this quote underlines the unbalanced relationships between the white and the black community in the United States with the former dominating the latter. To break this paradigm, there is a need to reinvigorate the black society with education.

In *Up From Slavery*, Booker T. Washington, a former slave, presents tripartite approach to education – intellectual, vocational, and moral. After the 1863's Emancipation Proclamation, which officially put an end to slavery in the U.S., many formerly enslaved people had to find their way in the American society and fulfill themselves. Booker T. Washington, one of these people, wrote an autobiographical *Up From Slavery* which chronicles his process of self-education and its impact on his growth as a free and functioning member of American society. Today, despite the abolition of institutionalized slavery, other forms of enduring mental slavery remain realities against which many people — especially those from former colonized countries — struggle in order to attain holistic development. For this former slave, the newly freed black people should develop their intellectual capacities, embrace hard work and show moral qualities so as to have a good stand in the American society. Indeed, various debates have been raised over the best forms of education to be promoted among former colonized countries in order to ensure balanced and fulfilled populations. Though no consensus has been reached yet, it is central to consider the dynamism of such education. The question is: how should courses be taught more rewardingly to ensure learners' use of critical thinking in finding necessary solutions to various social challenges? This query is the core purpose of the present essay. The essay analyzes the impact of cognition, vocational skills, and moral values on the holistic development of individuals and communities. It argues that education should enhance individuals' capacities, including knowledge (cognition), the practical application of knowledge (know-how), and ethical and moral values (know-how-to-live). This type of education engages the head, the hand and the heart.

Through the lens of Postcolonial theory, this paper analyzes various types of education and highlights the necessity of a balanced approach to education for both personal and community development. According to Shehla Burney: "Postcolonial theory operates on the notion that imperialism and colonial domination have affected the whole world,

not simply the colonized nations" (173-4). He adds: "Postcolonial analysis is critical of the discourse of cultural imperialism, which is manifested in several different spheres of thinking, from literary writing and criticism to historical and cultural analysis of artifacts and ideas" (Burney 174). No doubt, postcolonial theory is instrumental in analyzing educational trends for newly emancipated slaves seeking an integral development.

The paper is structured around three parts. While the first part shows the insufficiency of intellectual education for individual fulfillment, the second one focuses on the necessity to promote practical education. The third part advocates for a balanced education encompassing the development of the head, hand, and heart, a golden path to holistic development of both individuals and communities.

1. Limiting the Education of the Head

The education of the head simply means, in the context of this paper, intellectual education. This part argues that intellectual education is not enough for an individual's complete fulfillment. Admitting the great role intellectual education plays in a society's development, it underlines the limits of this kind of education. Truth to be told, intellectual education is really crucial for any society's development. Cognizant of this fact, governments and institutions invest many resources and much energy in transmitting knowledge at various levels. By investing in intellectual education, they strongly believe that this is a catalyzer for individuals to develop their cognitive abilities, critical thinking skills and knowledge, which are essential for economic and social development.

In *Up From Slavery*, Booker T. Washington portrays his personal journey from slavery to becoming an influential educator and leader in the African American community. This serves as a testimony to the power of intellectual education. Skills acquired through cognition equipped him with necessary determination to overcome barriers of poverty and discrimination in his community. He considers Black people's lack of intellectual education as a great mistake, arguing: "the coloured people, so largely without education, and wholly without experience in government, made a tremendous mistake, just as any people similarly situated would have done."¹ Obviously, Washington believes that the lack of intellectual education for Negroes constitutes a serious hindrance to their development. His use of "so largely without education" informs readers of how the whole black community is disconnected with intellectual education resulting in its negative impact on their progress. Thus, he views academic knowledge as a means for Blacks to access better positions in the white-dominated communities.

¹ Booker T. Washington (1901). *Up From Slavery*. New York: Airmont Publishing Company, p. 61. All subsequent references to this novel will be abbreviated as *Washington* followed by the page number

Washington believes that Negroes' access to higher education will empower them to the extent that white supremacists will hold them in high esteem. Educated black leaders will, no doubt, help promote progress and equality in the black communities. To witness, Washington himself, as an educated leader, calls for unity of Blacks and Whites, notwithstanding their skin color, in order to secure a sure and better progress. Interestingly, he is concerned with better progress, which is due to his being educated. In his "The Atlanta Exposition Address", he states: "we can be as separated as fingers, yet one as the hand in all things essential to mutual progress" (*Washington* 136). The foregoing underscores Washington's metaphorical call for both Whites and Blacks to work together for their communities' development. This insight stems from his intellectual education. The idea of mutual progress is key in considering the role of intellectual education for social development.

This paper insists that intellectual education is central to Blacks' development in a white-dominated society. It is calling black communities to study hard in order to be intellectually seated. Understanding the centrality of intellectual education in his personal life, Washington posits: "during my last year at Hampton every minute of my time that was not occupied with my duties as a janitor was devoted to hard study" (*Washington* 54). By informing his readers that he devoted every single minute of his time to hard study, Washington not only shows his awareness of the importance of intellectual education for his personal development but also encourages his fellow Blacks to get educated. Boosting one's intellectual abilities helps better the performance of manual tasks, as exemplified by Washington himself. This can be explained by the fact that the brain works as a catalyst and is the core of human's actions. So, a well-trained brain works better and more rewardingly. Intellectual education is crucial for black people's development in the United States.

However, in the wake of Washington, this paper argues that intellectual education is not sufficient for Blacks in their challenging white-dominated environment. Indeed, When Frederrick Douglas (1997) writes: "access to a good education and a broad range of experiences lead in advancing African Americans economically, politically as well as socially", he does not focus on intellectual education alone, but emphasizes its combination with practical education. It is this combination which offers "a comprehensive information base from which African Americans can draw liberatory knowledge to address the myriad problems they continue to face in the society" (Alridge 191). Clearly, intellectual education is not enough for an individual's fulfillment, particularly for Black in the United States. It needs an association of effective practical education.

2. Promoting Effective Education of the Hand

Booker T. Washington presents vocational education as an essential tool for economic growth in *Up From Slavery*. For him, vocational skills are key for economic independence when added to cognition. The education of the hand actually helps

acquire practical skills. Booker T. Gardner backs up this idea when he points out that Washington “thought, however, that it is important for students to pay their way and thus support themselves at least in part, in order to inculcate the spirit of self-help, thrift, and economic independence” (Gardner 512). For Washington, vocational training is important for African Americans’ fulfillment in a white-dominated society. He posits: “with few exceptions, the Negro youth must work harder and must perform his task even better than a white youth in order to secure recognition” (*Washington* 36). Reading between the lines, Blacks’ survival challenge in the United States is tougher than Whites’ one. For instance, the JBHE Foundation, Inc (98) unveils the hardship Blacks faced in engineering field:

From the earliest times, blacks were not believed to have the mental capacity, and particularly the precise mathematical skills, necessary to comprehend the complex subjects in the engineering curriculum. Just as blacks were never entrusted with the care or management of money, whites were reluctant to entrust black people with the planning and construction of the physical structures vital to the American economy and to the safety of people.

From the above, academic knowledge could not save Blacks in the white-dominated environment since they were not believed to comprehend complex subjects. Given these realities, they must work harder than their white counterparts, the only way for them to gain and secure recognition. Put differently, Blacks have to embrace manual work. The term “task” Washington uses in the previous quote strategically refers to manual work which implies vocational education.

Admittedly, manual work helps Blacks to secure recognition. This means effective education of the hand is a strong weapon to build an intrinsic relationship with Whites. After the 1863’s Emancipation Proclamation, which officially put an end to slavery in the U.S., many formerly enslaved people had to find their way in the American society and fulfill themselves. Booker T. Washington, one of these people, wrote an autobiographical *Up from Slavery* which chronicles his process of self-education and its impact on his development as a free and functioning member of American society. Today, despite the abolition of institutionalized slavery, other forms of enduring mental slavery remain realities against which many people — especially those from former colonized countries — struggle in order to attain holistic development. Indeed, while education of the head answers the question “what do you know?”, the one of the hand answers this query: “what can you do?” In this regard, he declares: “the individual who can do something that the world want done will in the end, make his way regardless of his race” (*Washington* 99). The foregoing confirms that “what can you do” education is determinant to Blacks’ recognition in the United States. One fathoms Washington’s fight for industrial education for the blacks: “For two hundred and fifty years, I believe the way for the redemption of the Negro was being prepared through industrial development. Through all those years the Southern white man did business with the Negro in a way that no one else has done business with him” (*Washington* 99). In essence, the few Blacks who worked with Whites were

those getting outstanding vocational skills, not just intellectual education. A typical example is the cleaning up training Washington got from Mrs. Ruffner, which he describes as a valuable education: "a valuable education I have ever gotten anywhere since. Even to this day I have never seen bits of paper scattered around a house or in a street that I do not want to pick them up at once" (*Washington* 38). This education is valuable indeed, as it not only helps Washington to have a link with the outsiders, but also pushes him to make his environment clean. Thus, it is important to promote the education of the hand in order to fill in the insufficiency of the education of the head.

As mentioned earlier, the individual's potentialities need to be enhanced through education. This paper sustains the thesis that knowledge is power. However, sometimes, intellectual knowledge does not bring food on the table. Rather, it creates idle people whose actions are limited to the mind. Washington is right when he argues that this form of education puts an individual in a weak position. As an illustration, consider the case of a black girl in the United States:

It seems to me that too often mere book education leaves the Negro young man or woman in a weak position. For example, I have seen a Negro girl taught by her mother to help her in doing laundry work at home. Later, when this same girl was graduated from the public schools or a high school and returned home she finds herself educated out of sympathy with laundry work, and yet not able to find anything to do which seems in keeping with the cost and character of her education (*Washington*, retrieved from <https://teachingamericanhistory.org>)

Certainly, purely academic education does not necessarily guarantee a job for an individual. The JBHE Foundation, Inc. presents a thought-provoking case of Robert Robinson Taylor that unveils the necessity to promote an education of the hand. Indeed, he graduated as the class valedictorian with a bachelor's of science degree in architecture in 1892. But because of his skin color, his services were not wanted by any white company. The Foundation narrates that "this brilliant young man had little choice but to remain at Tuskegee where he taught for 41 years" (*The JBHE Foundation, Inc.* 98). Washington employed the young Robert Robinson Taylor in Tuskegee Institute when all doors were closed to him. This illustration underlines the fact that Blacks' chances to be economically independent are reduced with intellectual education alone. In contrast, vocational training equips them for more job opportunities.

Here comes the importance of Washington's time at Hampton Institute in Virginia. Indeed, the year Washington spent in Hampton Institute shaped his vision of vocational education. The school focused on industrial education and taught students a range of practical skills, including carpentry, mechanics and agriculture. This resulted in his founding Tuskegee Institute in 1881 where he implemented his idea of enhancing vocational training for Blacks to gain their financial freedom. His belief is captured:

Washington was optimistic that the African-Americans could elevate their position in the society and could attract respect from the Whites only by the acquisition of practical skills. This belief forced him for advocating in favour of vocational training which could serve as a means to achieve economic independence (*Mishra, et.al* 8625).

So, in Tuskegee, black students were taught practical skills to allow them to become economically self-sufficient and improve their lives. This is commendable undertaking which showcases Washington's accomplishment of social responsibility. Gardner's comment is worth underlining:

Washington's outlook was an attempt to meet the problem of a people ill-equipped by the segregated system for either political leadership or economic progress. He was convinced that Negroes must prove themselves, must demonstrate tangibly and concretely that they are worthy of the blessings of emancipation (Gardner 506).

In short, Washington understood the place of vocational education in solving social problems.

As mentioned in Gardner's comment, his main purpose in promoting freed slaves' training in practical work is to ensure their political leadership and economic progress. So an effective education of the hand alongside the education of the head boosts both individual and social progress. However, there is a third form of education which paves way to a holistic development: the education of the heart.

3. Balancing Intellectual and Practical Education with the Education of the Heart

Science without conscience is but ruin of the soul. This old adage by the French author François Rabelais must appeal to educators. It alludes to moral implications in knowledge acquisition or its use. Put differently, it shows the importance of the education of the heart. Indeed, the education of the heart implies the transmission of moral values that shape an individual's heart for good. It is an education that helps develop human character, morally or spiritually, for an efficient application of knowledge. It leads to a balanced or holistic education.

Washington presents moral values as an essential component of African Americans' character development. For him, spirituality plays a great role in the growth of individuals. He believes that Bible reading is necessary for individuals to succeed in life, irrespective of their race or social status. He puts: "Before this I had never cared a great deal about it, but now I learned to love to read the Bible, not only for the spiritual help which it gives, but an account of it as literature" (*Washington* 50). For its implementation, Washington gives his own routine: "The lessons taught me in this respect took such a hold upon me that at the present time, when I am at home, no matter how busy I am, I always make it a rule to read a chapter or a portion of chapter in morning, before beginning the work of the day" (*Washington* 51). Based on the foregoing, reading the Scriptures will foster an individual's spirituality, allowing them to be morally considerate towards other people.

Washington's endeavor for African Americans' character development through the education of the heart makes sense as the latter have historically faced significant challenges and obstacles. They have been oppressed and dehumanized by the white folks. Thus, this essay uses the postcolonial theory to explore the distorted life of

African Americans. Put differently, they have been morally dislocated. As a matter of fact, they need sound moral education alongside intellectual and practical education in order to be whole. Brett G. Grant (148) concurs with Washington in this respect: "The development of a strong moral character was a central component of, Washington's educational philosophy." A sure thing, moral values provide a framework for African Americans' ethical behaviors. Leslie E. Laud affirms: "the colonists believed that personal encounter with Scriptures ensured individual salvation and ethical citizenship" (Laud 2). Understandably, a society needs not only intellectual citizens, but ethical ones as well. The term "colonists" refers to black slaves who recognized ethical transformation they gain from their contact with Scriptures.

Washington pinpoints some moral values necessary for the former slaves' development in the United States. For instance, he argues that the former slaves and their descendants must be self-reliant in order to succeed in the American society. He stresses the importance of perseverance and determination in the face of adversity, highlighting that the Negro must be non-violent and submissive. For Washington, "The wisest among any race understand that the agitation of questions of social equality is the extremest folly, and that progress in the enjoyment of all the privileges that will come to us must be the result of severe and constant struggle rather than of artificial forcing" (*Washington* 137). It is interesting to get the point in what Washington means here: instead of fighting for their social equality, individuals should rather fight for their progress. In other words, one should accept their social differences, put them aside, and face the challenges to their development.

Washington equally emphasizes the importance of honesty and integrity in his autobiography. For him, individuals must be honest with themselves and with others in order to be successful and respected. He believes that African Americans need to cultivate good habits to be successful in life. These habits, he argues, are important in both personal and professional settings, and they demonstrate an individual's level of responsibility and respect for others. An instance in Washington's honesty and integrity is worth mentioning for illustration: "One day, during the last of my stay in the restaurant, I found under one of the tables a crisp, new ten-dollars bill. I could hardly contain myself; I was so happy. As it was not my place of business, I felt it to be the proper thing to show the money to the proprietor. This I did" (*Washington* 50). By behaving this way, Washington establishes confidence which will lead to a bond of solidarity with the white community. This kind of deportment is essential for African Americans to gain broad range of economic development. So moral character formation must be at the heart of a balanced education.

Furthermore, Washington encourages his readers to have a positive and optimistic outlook on life. He argues that individuals must have faith in themselves and their ability to succeed, and that they must be willing to work hard and continuously strive for improvement. He states: "I have begun everything with idea that I could succeed, and I never had much patience with the multitudes of people who are always ready to

explain why one cannot succeed" (*Washington* 50). Many African Americans think they are inferior because of their skin color. This long-standing thought is preventing them from acting with the hope to succeed. However, in this quote, Washington shows how thinking positively opens the door to success.

Critical readers of *Up from Slavery* fathom what David Sehat calls the civilizing mission of Washington. Indeed, Washington is not only fostering an education of the head for black people in the United States, or its combination with the education of the hand alone. His mission consists in achieving a holistic development for the black community living in an appalling environment. In other words, he is fighting for holistic education for his fellow Blacks. Holistic education is the type of education which focuses on the development of the whole person. It includes education affecting positively the intellectual, emotional, social, and spiritual knowledge of individuals and communities. Holistic education promotes a balanced development of individuals as well as their relationships with their fellows, their natural environment, their inner-self etc. (Mahmoudi 178). Effective development in modern African societies requires such an education: equilibrium of intellectual, physical and spiritual education.

Indeed, this holistic education, which comes through balance of the education of the head, the hand and the heart, will enhance and prepare modern African societies to be confident, compassionate, and form individuals who can adapt to changing circumstances and make meaningful contributions to modern African societies. This is the case of Booker T. Washington who succeeded in getting this round-education, resulting in his making the difference between himself and his counterparts. A balanced education will create a positive learning environment for modern African societies and encourage critical thinking, creativity, and self-reflection. This approach to learning will help Africans and the African diaspora to better understand themselves, their communities, and the world around them in order to develop the skills they need to thrive academically and personally. In this regard, Gardner gives a synopsis of Booker T. Washington's philosophy of education:

Washington advocated that education must be centered in meaningful and relevant problem-solving activities. He concluded that knowledge is a tool for managing experiences and new situations confronting the individual. Washington did not believe in the artificial separation of subject matter. He also taught that education should extend beyond the mere walls of the educational enterprise and touch all aspects of life through many varied agencies (Gardner 509).

Actually, an effective education should impact all aspects of life. It must consider the head, the hand and the heart. It is only then that societies can achieve holistic development. Brett G. Grant (144) cogently sums up Washington's expectation in Tuskegee Institute:

Every student at Tuskegee was expected to learn some practical skill. This was an education of the hands. Every student was expected to be able to think for him or herself. This was an education of the head [...]. And lastly, every student was expected to leave Tuskegee with an impeccable sense of moral character. This was an education of the heart.

The three forms of education are needed in each person in order to push them to their full potentialities. As a matter of fact, Tuskegee Institute remains a model school not only in modern African societies but in the whole world, because it equips individuals with the education of the head, the hand and the heart.

CONCLUSION

This study has established the effectiveness of intellectual, vocational, and moral education in achieving the holistic development of individuals and communities. Using Postcolonial theory, it has analyzed Booker T. Washington's *Up From Slavery* as a case study to show that the kind of education that aims to boost the cognitive, vocational, and moral skills among minority groups is essential for modern, formerly colonized countries.

This paper has identified three key findings: first, intellectual education develops the cognition and therefore, helps to have rational leaders who can inspire individual and societal growth. Second, if vocational education complements intellectual education, it equips people to build sophisticated communities, achieve economic independence, and establish fruitful relationships with others. Lastly, the paper argues that moral education will be able to instill confidence and ethical grounding necessary for societies in building projects needed for development. Overall, balancing the education of the head, the hand, and the heart, as presented in Booker T. Washington's *Up From Slavery*, is a strong weapon for promoting the holistic development of modern African societies.

References

- Alridge, Derrick P. "Guiding philosophical Principles for a Duboisian-Based African American Educational Model." *The Journal of Negro Education*, vol. 68, no. 2, 1999, pp. 182-199.
- Burney, Shehla. "Conceptual Frameworks in Postcolonial Theory: Application for Educational Critique." *Counterpoints*, vol. 417, 2012, pp. 173-193.
- Dewey, John. *Experience and Education*. New York: Macmillan, 1938.
- Flinders, David. & Thornton, Stephen. *The Curriculum Studies Reader*. (4th Ed.) New York: Routledge, 2013.
- Gardner, Booker T. "The Educational Contributions of Booker T. Washington." *The Journal of Negro Education*, vol. 44, no. 4, 1975, pp. 502-518.
- Grant, Brett G. "Booker T. Washington's Educational Contributions to Contemporary Practices of Sustainable Development," *Open Review of Educational Research*, vol. 1, no.1, 2014, pp. 144-159, DOI: 10.1080/23265507.2014.986188.

- Laud, Leslie E. "Education in American: 1600s-1800s." *The Journal of Education*, vol. 179, no. 2, 1997, pp. 1-10.
- Mahmoudi, Sirous. "Holistic Education: An Approach for 21 Century." *International Education Studies*, vol. 5, no. 2, 2012, pp. 178-186.
- Mishra, Rasabihari et.al. "Locating the Self: An Analysis of Booker T. Washington's 'Up from Slavery.'" *Library Progress International*, vol.44, no.3, 2024, pp. 8622-8628.
- Sehat, David. "The Civilizing Mission of Booker T. Washington." *The Journal of Southern History*, vol. 73, no. 2, 2007, pp. 323-62. JSTOR, <http://www.jstor.org/stable/27649400>. Accessed 24 Dec. 2024.
- Washington, Booker T. *Up From Slavery*. New York: Airmont Publishing Company, 1901.
- Washington, Booker T. "Industrial Education for The Negro," retrieved from <https://teachingamericanhistory.org>. On November 20, 2023.